

PREPARING TO FAIL

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This is the season in my line of work when the final group selected to enter next year's veterinary program has received their happy news and are arriving for the first weeks of introduction to the city and program. With [1138 candidates this year for 225 places in the limited-enrollment program in Utrecht](#), it is one of the most highly selective programs in the Netherlands. These students are rightfully elated, and I look forward to meeting them at the start of the semester.

This year, however, I'm seeing this through a different lens since I now have friends with children old enough to have gone through the selection process for various highly selective programs: human medicine, pharmacy, veterinary medicine... and many of them are now going to start next year with Plan B, as they were in the vast majority who didn't get into the program of their first choice.

I myself am also on the Ferris wheel of having sent away many, many grant applications last year for highly competitive instruments. Each application was a learning experience and brought new collaborations, ideas for manuscripts, reflections, and energy- and then went into “the system” for a few months... and then one by one, the “you scored very high but unfunded” came back. This is part of the game, and I will revise and continue on, but rejection after rejection absolutely wore me down this spring.

As I am taking in the different perspectives, I wondered how well we talk about failure with our students. Failures can happen in low-stakes assignments in the classroom or in high-stakes clinical situations. For medical professionals, mistakes can be carried for years, as was described in [a powerful set of interviews with medical doctors in a Dutch newspaper](#) who described from first-hand experience what happens to the practitioner when things go “wrong”. Learning how to cope and learn, is critical for students, but as Eckstein and colleagues point out in their recent paper on “the pedagogy of failure” (Eckstein et al., 2023), we as educators believe that failure helps us grow as people and professionals, yet don’t often have the time in educational practice to help students reflect and grow from failure.

In a recent review on learning through failure (Rawle et al., 2025), Rawle and colleagues clearly laid out the role of institutions and settings in learning from failure: if you don’t have the resources to aid resilience, or the recognition of power dynamics and privilege, then failure becomes an insurmountable hurdle for the learners. We need to put these into place, since we all recognize that with the right support, failure can be a learning- or indeed transformative- experience.

In a few weeks I’ll take up teaching the new cohort, the “winners” in the veterinary medicine selection process- and during the 6-year program many failures, big and small, will happen within this group that got through the selection process. Recognizing that we all both fail and succeed at different times and in different contexts, is one of the starting points.

Eckstein, L. E., Finaret, A. B., & Whitenack, L. B. (2023). Teaching the Inevitable: Embracing a Pedagogy of Failure. *TEACHING & LEARNING INQUIRY-THE ISSOTL JOURNAL*, 11.

<https://doi.org/10.20343/teachlearninqu.11.16>

Rawle, F., Laliberte, N., & Guadagnolo, D. (2025). An interdisciplinary review of learning through failure in higher education. *EDUCATIONAL REVIEW*.

<https://doi.org/10.1080/00131911.2025.2475829>